
Machinery development & testing

IRRI offers plans for time-saving, labor-saving paddy sled

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Engineers of the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) have developed a simple sled that permits rice farmers with power tillers to speed up harrowing and ease the drudgery of tillage in flooded paddies. The sled attaches directly to the tiller and allows the operator to ride above the surface of the mud.

The sled increases labor productivity by about 40% above that of machine-harrowing without it. Labor productivity is approximately five times that of a farmer working behind a water buffalo. One machine operator can perform the work usually handled by two. Energy

Paddy sled attaches to power tiller and allows operator to ride above surface of the mud.

monitoring tests at IRRI indicate that 70% of the human energy expended during land preparation is used in walking through the mud.

The sled fits any power tiller equipped

with conventional draft implements. It costs approximately US\$10. Requests for plans should be addressed directly to the Agricultural Engineering Department at IRRI.

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two paragraphs and a table, figure, or photograph. They are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

Individuals, organizations, and media are invited to quote or reprint articles or excerpts from articles in the IRRN. Duplicate prints of photos and illustrations are available to media on request from the Office of Information Services, IRRI. Persons who wish additional details of information presented in IRRN should write directly to the authors.

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